

Effect of Parents Involvement on Cookery Skills Development of Grade 9 Students

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Abstract. This study aimed to determine the effect of parents involvement on cookery skills development of Grade 9 students. This study made use of quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation. The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This study was conducted in Pedro Arches National High School, Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study were the 90 grade nine pupils – 45 are from section A which comprised the controlled group and 45 are from section B composed the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is heterogeneous therefore pupils of sections A and B have identical range of performance. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the utilization of parents involvement has increased the cookery skills of grade nine students. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

KEY WORDS

1. Parents Involvement 2. Cookery Skills 3. Development

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1. Introduction

Parents involvements is imperative for students' skills development. Having parents helps students feel more motivated and showing confidence in doing the task in the class. Education begins at home. The responsibility to socialize and educate children is a shared obligation between parents and school. In order for a child to reach academic achievement, parents must be involved and participate in the educational process. The more parental involvement, the more students are likely to become a productive member of society as well as in academics (Cole, 2024). Parental involvement is essential for child's successful learning and development of essential skills. They nurture self-regulated behaviors by satisfying the necessary needs of their child. School-home relationship be more structured in order to create awareness about how to teach and coach self-regulatory process at home to their children by satisfying their psychological needs to make their learning progress more vibrant. (Farooq Asim, 2020). Parents possessed good motivation to assist children's in learning by understanding their important role and having confidence in accompanying children's learning activities (Novianti, Puspitasari,

Maria, 2021). Though there appear to be significant benefits associated with parent involvement throughout a child's education, in recent years, concerns have been expressed regarding whether some parents are too involved in their children's lives. These "helicopter" parents are believed to swoop down at a moment's notice whenever their children's are in distress and may inadvertently interfere with children's ability to tackle challenges and solve their own problems (Van Ingen et al., 2023) Parents should be more intensive in assisting, accompanying, and guiding their children so that their motivation and academic performance can be enhanced. Teachers and school give more fruitful collaboration between schools to facilitate their needs and potentials (Duman, Aydin, Ozfidan, 2018). In Malaysia, a research study titled "The Influence of Parental Involvement on Hands-on Skills Development in Malaysian Students" was conducted to examine the role of parents in fostering the acquisition of hands-on skills among students in Malaysia. The findings of the study indicated that parental engagement in their children's hands-on activities had a substantial positive impact on the development of their skills. The researchers underscored the significance of parental support and engagement in cultivating an environment that is conducive to experiential learning (Omar et al., 2018). Furthermore, a separate study conducted within the same country examined the effects of parental engagement

on the enhancement of practical skills among secondary school students in Malaysia. The research emphasized that parents who actively participated in interactive activities with their children had a positive impact on their problem-solving skills, creativity, and critical thinking abilities. The researchers proposed that it would be beneficial to promote parental involvement in order to facilitate the development of students' hands-on skills (Tan Lim, 2020). In the Philippines, a study examines the influence of parental involvement on the development of technical vocational skills among secondary school students in the Philippines. The results of the study indicated that students who had parents who were highly engaged in their education exhibited greater proficiency in technical vocational skills in comparison to students whose parents were less involved. This implies that the provision of parental support and guidance plays a pivotal role in cultivating the technical vocational capabilities of students (Santos Cruz, 2020). In the Division of Davao del Sur, particularly in Pedro A. Arches National High School, students in grade 9 cookery finds difficult to cook the menu assigned to them. The researcher being a teacher in the above-mentioned exhaust her effort in looking for a strategy to make learners develop their skills in cookery. Hence, this study of parent's involvement in teaching cookery particularly in cookery skills development of Grade 9 students.

2. Methodology

This chapter discussed the researcher method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure and the data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study made use of the quasi experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good

design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This design is represented as follows:

0₁ x 0₂

0₃ x 0₄

Where:

- 0₁ - Pretest of the experimental group
- 0₂ - Posttest of the experimental group
- 0₃ - Pretest of the controlled group
- 0₄ - Posttest of the controlled group
- - Non-random assignment of subjects
- X - Treatment applied in the experimental group

Distribution of Respondents

	Subjects	No. of Pupils
1	Section A	45
2	Section B	45
	Total	90

2.2. *Research Respondents*—This study will be conducted in Pedro Arches National High School, Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study will be the 90 grade nine students – 45 are from section A which will be the controlled group and 45 are from section

B which will be the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is heterogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study makes use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This study will utilized the new normal learning modality. It is a blended learning where teacher gave module at the same meet the learners online but adhering to the protocols of Inter-agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher has to meet the learners online for a follow up session of what has been printed in the module. The pre and post-performance test consist of a 45 –item test will

eventually determine the cookery skills of the research subjects. The pretest will be administered to all subjects prior to the treatment. The pretest will be very helpful to assess the cookery skills of the grade nine students. On the hand, post test will be administered to measure the effect of the treatment. To determine the cookery skills of the grade nine students, the following continuum will be used based on DepEd rating system.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of data gathering procedure, the researcher will draft a letter seeking for permission that this research study be conducted were sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao Del Sur, Dr. Nelson Lopez, CESO V and the school principal of Pedro Arches Na-

tional High School. While letters seeking for permission were delivered to the Schools Division Superintendent and the school principal concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and have it validated by the experts preferably the experts of the study. After permission has been granted that this study be con-

Criteria for Student Performance

Interval	Scale	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced: The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills, and understandings and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient: The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency: The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing: The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning: The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

ducted at Pedro Arches National High School and after the research questionnaire has been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher will administer pretest to both controlled and experimental class and eventually commences her experiment. After three

weeks of experimentation, the researcher will administer posttest to both sections. Scores of the subjects will be submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher will make analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools will be used in the analysis and interpretation the responses in this study. Mean will be used to describe the cookery skills of

the grade nine students. Eta square will be used to measure the magnitude of effect of parents involvement on the cookery skills of grade nine students.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussion of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners and the Significant Relationship of the pre-tests and Post-tests Scores.

Pre-Test Score of Learners Table 1 disclosed the pre-test scores of the grade nine students. The controlled group got the mean of 24.6 or

Beginning while the experimental group got the mean of 25.4 or Beginning.

Table 1. Pre-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group	45	24.6	54.66	Beginning
Experimental Group	45	25.4	56.44	Beginning

It can be gleaned from the table that during pre-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group although both belongs Beginning level. This finding is congruent to the idea of Hickman (2021) who said that with regard to the acquisition of general skills, the optimal period for acquiring new skills is during the developmental stage spanning from childhood to early adolescence. The efficacy of this principle has been demonstrated in various domains, including education, wherein the early acquisition of skills related to learning has been found to exert a beneficial influence on academic progress in the subjects of mathematics and reading. Given the aforemen-

tioned context pertaining to other essential life skills, it is imperative to explore the potential correlation between early exposure to computer science education and its subsequent influence on dietary habits in later stages of life. This concept aligns with the argument that modeling serves as a crucial mechanism by which parental involvement influences behavior. It is anticipated that engaging in conversations between parents and children will have an impact on the attitudes of students, potentially influencing their behavior as well. Consequently, this influence is expected to result in enhanced academic performance (Hoover-Dempsey, 2021).

Table 2. Post-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group	45	36.30	80.66	Developing
Experimental Group	45	37.97	84.37	Approaching Proficiency

Shown in table 2 are the post-test scores of the grade nine students. The controlled group got the mean of 36.30 or Developing while the experimental group gained the mean of 37.97 or Approaching Proficiency. It can be gleaned from the table that during post-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group. It got a mean rating increase of 12.57 from a mean rating of 25.4 to 37.97. This means that experimental group has a far better performance than the controlled group. This finding is congruent to the idea of Hill Taylor (2021) who cited that when students are educated about food preparation procedures and various methods in schools, they tend to approach the subject with a level of seriousness

comparable to other academic disciplines such as mathematics. This will encourage individuals to transition their skills and apply them in their personal environment, thereby engaging in further practice. Consistent practice at home on the skills acquired at school will yield proficient cooks, unlike those who solely acquire cooking skills within a home setting. Students whose families were involved in school tended to express higher aspirations for their educations and careers. These students were more likely to set career goals in scientific, technical and professional areas. They had a strong commitment to life-long education than whose parents were not involved (Johnston 2020).

Table 3. Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	37	-5.42	.0351	Significant

Table 3 shows the test on the significant difference between the pretest and post-test score of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.42 with a p-value of .0351 which is lesser than .05 level of significance which means that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post test scores of the grade nine students. This implies that parents involvement in teaching cookery nine have contributed the effectiveness in teaching the subject which is revealed by the scores of the grade nine students. This finding is in line with the statement of Wherry (2020) who said that Cookery is an area in Home Economics that encompasses the practical application and mastery of techniques

involved in the preparation and cooking of various types of food. This subject encompasses the instruction of food nutrients, ethical considerations related to food, proper methods for safe food storage, and the principles of food preparation and handling. Additionally, this encompasses the domains of budgeting, food preservation, and the culinary industry. A student who receives effective motivation from their teacher may develop a strong foundation in the field of cookery, potentially leading to future opportunities in Food and Nutrition Management, as well as careers as Dieticians in healthcare settings or within corporate organizations. Additionally, such students may also pursue professions as

Nutritionists. Parental involvement not only enhances academic performance, but it also has a positive influence on student attitude and behavior. A parent’s interest and encouragement in a child’s education can affect the child’s attitude toward school, classroom conduct, self-

esteem and motivation. It can make difference at all level. A child may consider going to college more seriously when parents show interest in the child’s academic achievements (Degado, 2019).

Table 4. Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Grade 6 Students

N	t-value	Eta2	Descriptive Value	Decision
45	-4.28	0.421	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

Table 4 highlights the test of parents involvement on the development of cookery skills of grade nine students. It generated an Eta2 value of 0.421 which signifies large effect. This implies that teachers should look for a strategy in teaching cookery subject to develop the cooking skills of the students. Teaching cookery as a subject is not merely about teaching individuals how to prepare meals; rather, it is about imparting essential life skills, fostering health and well-being, and promoting cultural understanding. To ensure the development of skills, the teacher has to look for a strategy that would contribute to the success of teaching and learning process in the subject. It is crucial to acknowledge that parent involvement can manifest in

various forms, including engagement with the child, interaction with school personnel, or collaboration with other parents. This recognition is significant as different strategies of involvement may yield disparate outcomes. One of the perplexing elements within the literature pertains to the multitude of diverse conceptualizations of parent involvement that are utilized, spanning across various domains (child, school, parents), with limited discourse regarding the resulting implications. What is the significance of this? Certain types of parental involvement are likely to have a greater impact on student attitudes and behaviors, whereas other types are more likely to have a greater impact on academic achievement (Long, 2019).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displays the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made. This study sought to determine the effect of parents involvement on the cookery skills development of grade nine students.

4.1. Findings—This study made use of quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of

the study are intact group of learners. This study was conducted in Pedro Arches National High School, Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study were the 90 grade nine pupils – 45 are from section A which comprised the controlled group and 45 are from section B composed the experimental group. The composition

of these two sections is heterogeneous therefore pupils of sections A and B have identical range of performance. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the utilization of parents involvement has increased the cookery skills of grade nine students. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The pre-test scores of the grade nine students both the controlled and experimental groups is at the Beginning level. The post-test scores of the controlled group is at the Developing level while the post test scores of the experimental group is at the Approaching Proficiency level.

4.3. *Recommendations*—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are of-

fered: It is recommended that teachers teaching Cookery nine should used parent involvement as a strategy that would further develop the cookery skills of students in order to make the teaching of cookery meaningful. If learners take part in the learning process by experiencing the unfolding of the lesson, then he will appreciate the concept being develop, thus, he is learning. The school heads should promote the use of parent involvement as a strategy that would engage the child actively in the learning process as it is revealed in the study that it is effective especially on vocational or practical subject, as it focuses on developing specific skills. A school policy about the utilization of parents involvement can be issued. Besides, he can invite the teacher-researcher to demoteach during LAC session using parents involvement as a strategy in teaching. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the use of role play as a strategy in teaching will be conducted. Another dimension in teaching can serve as another indicator.

5. References

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